

FABRICATION OF LARGE SCALE BRAIDED COMPOSITE WITH I-SHAPED STRUCTURE

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SUMMARY: In these days, it is expected that textile preforms are applied to large scale composite structure since they have good stability and drapability. In this paper, the method to fabricate large braided composite was proposed. Firstly the width of braided fabric when a type and a number of fiber bundle was changed was measured. As the result, it was evident that the width of braided fabric was narrow and huge braiding machine with large number of spindles is necessary to fabricate large braided fabric. In this study the method which link braided fabric transversely with kited technique was introduced to fabricate a large braided fabric without using a huge braided machine. Using this knitted technique, braided fabrics can be linked without injuring reinforcements. Tensile test of linked braided fabric was carried out and it was evident that fabricating large braided composite without decreasing strength was possible using this link method.

KEYWORDS: CAE, braid, large composite structure, link, knitted technique, loop stitch, tensile test, I-beam

INTRODUCTION

The properties of fiber reinforced plastic (FRP) are decided not only by the combination of matrix and reinforcing materials but also by the unique geometry of the reinforcements. The geometry of the reinforcements has been investigated in addition to development of fiber and resin. Composite materials reinforced with fabric preforms made by either woven, braided or knitted fabrics are currently being considered as alternatives to tape laminates. "Textile" composites can be defined as composite materials reinforced with textile fabrics such as woven, knitted and braided fabrics. Manufacturing process for textile composites could also be automated, so it could potentially lead to lower costs. In textile forming technique not only two-dimensional plate shape but also thick or three-dimensional shape can be fabricated. These textile preforms can be applied in structural composites with complex shapes, since they have good stability and drapability, and can be fabricated directly to their final shapes. Such fabric reinforced textile composites have potential for improved out-of-plane stiffness, strength, delamination resistance and toughness properties. It has been expected that textile composites are used widely as structural parts in various fields from these reasons.

There are many published papers related to textile composites. They are divided into three categories; one is designing a new fabric that includes three dimensional weaving fabric, 2.5 dimensional warp knitted fabric and so on. The second one is developing a new machine that can correspond to the new fabrics. The third one is mechanical properties of textile composites such as static properties and impact properties. In this category numerical

modeling of textile composites is included. According to these classifications we have developed CAE system for braided composites as shown in Fig.1.

Fig. 1: CAE system for braided composites

In braided composites there are two basic fabrics; cord braiding and flat braiding. Determination of dimension of these fabrics such as width and thickness are very difficult problem because they greatly depend on not only fiber characteristics such as type of fibers, number of filaments, diameter of filaments but also weaving structure as fiber orientation angle, density of weaving structure and so on. Therefore designing the fabrics is needed as shown in flow chart of CAE system, and detail of this problem would be mentioned in the latter section. Another particular problem in the braided composites is that one machine can fabricate a specific braided fabric when materials type is fixed. The machine with large number of spindles can fabricate large braided fabric, however this large machine can not fabricate small braided fabric in proper fiber orientation state. Of course, small machine can not make large fabric. That means applicable ability of braiding is very small in terms of machine. According these circumstances in order to expand application field of braided composites wider an attempt that is fabricating large braided structure by using small machine was made in this study. Concretely, large braided composite with I-shaped structure was fabricated by using existing braiding machine in braiding technique and linking machine in knitting technique. First width of flat braided fabrics was examined by changing fiber types. After our basic concept of fabricating large braided structure was mentioned, some experimental results were described. Here it was clear that proposed linking method was very effective. Finally large I beam was appeared.

Dimension of Braided Fabric

In this section the width of flat braided fabrics using some kinds of fiber bundles was measured. The schematic of flat braided fabric is shown in Fig.2. Flat braided fabric has two

dimensional shape like a belt. The fiber bundles are continuously oriented in this fabric because they reverse themselves at the side edge. Therefore, when tensile load applies to flat braided fabric, all the fibers bare the load, so that it can become a string. The fibers will change their orientation angles smaller and then the width will become narrow. This point is the most important point for braided fabric. Changing orientation angle leads to changing fabric width. Moreover there are many different weaving structures. The surface of braided fabric shows a zig-zag pattern since the fiber bundles alternately pass over and under each other. Fig.3 shows repeating pattern in braided fabric, and (a) is Diamond braid where a fiber bundle continuously passes over one fiber bundle and then under one fiber bundle of the opposing group. Whereas Fig.3(b) shows Regular braid in which one fiber bundle passes two fiber bundles. The width of flat braided fabric depends on these braided patterns greatly.

Fig. 2: Schematic of flat braided fabric

(a) Diamond braid

(b) Regular braid

Fig. 3: Braided pattern

Fiber bundles used in this experiment were glass fiber bundles with 2000 filaments and 900 filaments. The diameter of a filament $17.0\mu\text{m}$. For Diamond braid the machine with 43 spindles was used and for Regular braid the machine with 85 spindles was used. Also, two different loading conditions were selected for changing fiber orientation angle; one was light weight and the other was heavy weight. Table 1 shows measurement results of width in each case. According to these results the widths in the cases of heavy weight are smaller than those in the case of light weight. The maximum value was 82.0mm and this was a limitation by using these material systems and machines.

Table 1: Measurement results of width of flat braided fabric

Type of Fiber Bundle	Weight	Braided Pattern	Braiding Angle	Width (mm)
900 Filaments	Light Weight	Diamond Braid	24°	37.0
		Regular Braid	28°	53.0
	Heavy Weight	Diamond Braid	15°	25.5
		Regular Braid	20°	36.0
2000 Filaments	Light Weight	Diamond Braid	28°	52.3
		Regular Braid	26°	82.0
	Heavy Weight	Diamond Braid	21°	35.0
		Regular Braid	17°	54.5

Basic Concept for Large Braided Structure

One of solutions for fabricating large braided composites was to make wider flat braided fabrics. When we can fabricate wider fabrics, that technique will be applied to various fields. Our basic concept for large braided structure in this paper was to link narrow flat braided fabrics. Accordingly very wider fabrics in any dimension can be produced by narrow one. Of course this system does not need huge machine with large number of spindles.

There are many linking method such as lacing stitch and loop stitch so on.(1) In this paper for linking knitted fabric technique was applied. This technique is similar to looping stitch technique. The schematic drawing of knitted link method is shown in Fig.4. This system has some superior points than other technique for linking fabrics. One is that braided fibers do not have some damages in linking process. This is very important point for mechanical properties of braided composites. In lacing stitch technique reinforced fibers suffer some damages and finally reduce their strength. As shown in Fig.4 knitted fibers go through braided fibers at the reversing point, so that knitted fibers do not make any damage on the braided fibers.

Fig. 4: Schematic drawing of knitted link method

Experiments

Fibers used in the experiments was glass fiber bundles with 2000 filaments and flat braided fabric was fabricated by the machine with 85 spindles. Fiber orientation angle to longitudinal direction was 38 degree. Linking was made by using dial linking machine as shown in Fig.5. This machine is a commercial available machine and is not special machine for linking. In this experiment aramid fiber was used for linking fibers. Three different linking methods were adopted as shown in Fig. 6; one was L shaped linking (L type) and the second one was single lap type link (S type), finally the third method was multi linked method (M type).(2) In these developed linking methods linking fibers do not make any damage on the braided fibers. After linking two flat braided fabrics, resin was impregnated into the fabrics and cured. The linked part was seemed to be the weakest part in the large braided structure. Therefore in order to the effects of linking part on the composite properties tensile tests were performed. For comparison, transverse strength of flat braided composites was also measured. Dimensions of specimens are 30 mm of width , 80 mm of gauge length and 1.6 mm of thickness.

Fig. 5: Dial knitted machine

Fig. 6: Linking method

Results

The experimental results are shown in Table 2. Also the fracture aspects of each specimen are shown in Fig.7. The strength of L type was the lowest and the strength increased in order of S type and M type. Surprisingly, the strength of M type was higher than transverse strength (53MPa). The transverse specimen was failed at the middle of the specimen and the crack inclined to the loading direction. In the cases of L type and S type specimens the fracture occurred at the linked part and finally linked fibers were stretched. On the other hand M type specimen did not exhibit fracture at the linked part and the aspect was similar to the transverse specimen.

Fig. 7: Fracture aspects of each specimen

Table 2: Tensile strength of each link type

Link Type	Strength (MPa)
L Type	26
S Type	37
M Type	69
Non Link (Transverse Direction)	53

According to detail observation of fiber orientation state in these specimens, there were two possible explanations for the strength differences between transverse specimen and M type specimen. The transverse specimen was cut out from the center on flat braided fabrics, whereas the linked specimens were from the edge of the fabrics. Fig. 8 shows the schematic drawings of fiber orientation state in flat braided fabric. Normally fiber orientation states are divided into three regions; both side edge regions and the center region. Fiber orientation angle in each region is different. At the center both fiber bundles which across each other have same angle and at the side edge one group have low angle and the other has large angle to the loading direction (transverse direction). In the linked specimen there are some fibers oriented at small angle to loading direction, so that there was possibility that the strength of the M type specimen was higher than that of transverse specimens. Also in the transverse specimen the fibers were cut at the edge, whereas in the M type specimen the fibers continuously oriented through linking fibers between tabs. This state was similar to the specimen to longitudinal specimen in which reinforcing fibers orient through out the specimen from one end to the other end. This result was one of possible reason for the strength differences. Consequently, M type linked method was very useful for fabricating large scale braided structure without decrease the strength.

Fig. 8: Fiber orientation state in flat braided fabric

Large Scale I beam Braided Structure

In the I-shaped beam, connecting part between flange part and web part is the weakest point, so that our basic concept for braiding, that fiber continuously oriented throughout the products, is applied to the connecting part in our product. According to our previous paper the I beam posses higher bending strength than aluminum. For fabricating large scale I beam, T-shaped braided fabric and flat braided fabric were linked together. At the connecting part between flange part and web part T-shaped braided fabric was used, so that the fiber bundle oriented continuously from flange part to web part as shown in Fig. 9. Our final product of I beam at the moment was shown in Fig. 10 in which the thickness was 3 mm, the height was 400 mm and width of flange was 400 mm. Further mechanical properties of these large scale products were measured.

Fig. 9: Structure of large scale I beam

Fig. 10: Final product of large scale I beam

CONCLUSION

In this paper a method which can fabricate large scale braided structure was presented. Knitting technology was applied for linking narrow flat braided fabrics, and three kinds of linking methods were proposed. M type linking provided higher strength than normal braided fabrics. According to proposed method a big lack of braided composites could be solved, so that it was believed that further usage of braided composites would be expanded.

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